

PROBLEMS AND PRACTICES IN SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT OF STUDENTS AT HOME

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ABSTRACT

This research aimed to investigate the problems and practices in solid waste management of students at home in terms of the 7Rs. It also explored on the relationship between these variables and some personal profile. The respondents of the study were the 169 Bachelor of Science in Agriculture and Bachelor of Science in Forestry students of Negros Oriental State University – Pamplona Extension. The researchers utilized the descriptive–correlational method, used a self-made questionnaire, and employed weighted mean, Chi-square, and Spearman’s Rank-order Correlation Coefficient. The findings of the study revealed that the extent of problems encountered by the students in SWM at home is “moderate” in terms of insufficient sorting of SW and attitude while it is “high” in terms of low awareness of proper SWM, poor dumping practices, and poor coordination on proper SWM. Accordingly, the study disclosed that the extent of practices of the students on the 7Rs of SWM is “high” in terms of rethink, reuse, repair, regift, and recycle yet it is “moderate” in terms of refuse and reduce. It was also revealed that there is a significant relationship between the students’ problems and the following practices in the SWM: rethink, refuse, reduce, reuse, regift, and recycle. All in all, it was found out that the educational attainment of the mothers of the students is significantly related to their problems and practices in SWM.

Keywords: *solid waste management, reduce, reuse, recycle, refuse, rethink, regift, repair*

INTRODUCTION

Management of waste is recognized globally as among the generation's major critical issues that affect our environment (Goel, 2017). This pressing problem is brought about by the world's increasing population as rural communities migrate to cities to seek opportunities. Knickmeyer (2020) mentioned that it was predicted by the United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UN DESA) that 68% of the population of the world will reside in cities by 2050. Accordingly, understanding the social factors influencing household behavior is crucial to building and enhancing municipal solid waste management systems (MSWMS). This growing problem in solid waste management will threaten public health in general as unsegregated wastes are just dumped in open landfills (Parkar et al., 2021). This global problem caused by exponential urban growth can greatly contribute to waste management problems, resulting in unsustainable development, with significant consequences in low-income countries (Debrah et al., 2021).

Increased solid waste production is also an issue in the Philippines since it is a dynamic country with a rapid economy due to increasing urbanization (Molina & Catan, 2021). Correspondingly, the guidelines and structure for the nation's management of solid waste was established by Republic Act (RA) 9003 on Ecological Solid Waste Management (ESWM) Act of 2000. One of the crucial aspects of this republic act is the formal delegation of the management of waste to local levels, the mandatory termination of illegal dumpsites, purchase of machineries, and the minimization as well as effective management of solid wastes (Domingo & Manejar, 2021). However, Galarpe (2017) pointed out that the local government entities failed to competently implement RA 9003 due to the absence of institutional waste management structures because of insufficient funds. He furthered that widespread usage of landfills and dump sites indicates these shortcomings in implementing solid waste management.

Several studies on Solid Wastes were conducted but these only focused on characterization and its management status and on raising awareness of solid waste management. These studies were centered within the community and schools, however, the current study focused on solid waste management at home because the researchers strongly believed that good values begin at home. The results of this study served as the basis for crafting an action plan that will benefit students, faculty and staff, and the parents. The observable outcomes are the development of sustainable SWM policy and procedures and reimplementation of University Memorandum Number 12, s. 2018, improved SWM awareness of students, which they can practice at home, interactive lessons integrating SWM, labeled trash bins on the campus, and extension programs to educate parents on SWM.

The researchers believe that this study can help reinforce the program on management of solid waste through formal training which leads to sustainability. The involvement of students in the practice of SWM and enhancing their sense of cooperation, responsiveness and teamwork are essential tools that will instill a culture of transforming

responsible waste management among them and help thereby reducing waste in their households.

Various literature and studies on the problems and practices in solid waste management are discussed in this section. Moreover, it connects the works of other authors to acquire concepts that are relevant to the study.

Solid waste. The term "solid waste" refers to garbage from commercial, industrial, mining, and agricultural operations and community activities (EPA, 2019). The study of Gelan (2021) supports the current finding that most of the solid waste is produced from households, followed by shopping malls, street cleaning, factories/ industries, lodging establishments, and medical facilities, respectively. The same is also confirmed in the recent study that was conducted by Khalid et al. (2022), which claims that most of solid waste produced within developing nations generates from homes, followed by the commercial or market sectors.

According to Chadar and Keerti (2017), the classifications of solid wastes are *municipal*, *industrial*, and *hazardous*. Household activities of human beings produce *municipal waste*. Meanwhile, industrial activities produce *industrial waste*. Lastly, the substances that cause hazard to plants, animals, and human beings produce *hazardous waste*. Correspondingly, Chand (2019) noted that the categories of solid wastes are *hazardous* and *non-hazardous*, which are, in turn, split into *biodegradable* and *non-biodegradable*. Municipal solid wastes include paper, plastic, cloth, metal, glass, and other organic materials, along with waste from homes and businesses. Although they must be collected and processed separately, hospital and nursing home wastes are included in the municipal solid waste in most cities and municipalities.

One of the many social and environmental issues that student households deal with is solid garbage. This is a pressing problem at global, national, and local levels because poor solid waste management can result in flooding, water shortages, water contamination, adverse health effects, and rehabilitation expenses that could be too much for the municipality to handle (Koop & van Leeuwen, 2017). In like manner, Chadar and Keerti (2017) confirmed some of the environmental impacts and health hazards caused by solid waste problems. These environmental impacts include contaminated liquids from dumps that permeate the ground and pollute groundwater; roadside trash left by scavengers and stray animals which causes aesthetic damage; burned plastic and rubber produce foul smells; and organic solid wastes produce foul odor during decomposition and pollute the environment. Meanwhile, various illnesses, including endemic typhus, bacillary dysentery, diarrhea, amoebic dysentery, plague, salmonellosis, trichinosis, jaundice, hepatitis, and gastro enteric disorders, are caused by health hazards. Therefore, controlling solid waste is crucial to lowering solid waste pollution and establishing a clean and pollution-free environment.

In the same way, management of solid waste has a direct impact on the environment and the consequent economic implications (Kaza et al., 2018). Inadequate garbage collection, improper disposal, and inappropriate facility placement can have a significant negative impact on the environment and human health at local and regional

levels. Consequently, solid waste contributes to climate change and ocean pollution on a global scale. A similar finding can be found in the study of Chand (2019), where poor solid waste management resulted in air, water, and soil pollution. Similarly, solid wastes may cause diseases as these wastes are breeding places for many vectors. Substances like polythene bags block drain pipes, paralyzing the drainage system. Lastly, stray animals could ingest harmful substances from food waste, which may result in many diseases and sudden death of these animals, and further increase solid waste.

Biodegradable waste. The term "biodegradable waste" refers to any organic waste that breaks down by the action of microorganisms, such as waste from the kitchen and garden, as well as waste from sanitary products, vegetable waste, and so on (Parkar et al., 2021).

Particularly, the study of Lunag and Elauria (2021) analyzed the biodegradable waste generated at home as a first step toward developing sustainable organic management alternatives. Their findings showed that a household with three to nine people produces between 0.04 and 0.31 kilograms of biodegradable waste per person per day, with a weighted average of 0.1122 kilograms. A household with five people can produce an average of 0.55 kg per day, mainly food scraps, followed by kitchen waste made up of vegetables and fruits, raw meat and fish, yard/garden materials, and wet papers. In addition, they noted that family size is correlated positively with household generation and negatively with per capita generation. Importantly, their research supports decentralized biological treatment as a realistic way to reduce and divert trash.

On the one hand, there are good and bad practices for biodegradable waste disposal. Separating biodegradable trash, dumping it in a compost pit, and turning it into plant fertilizers are all good practices to reduce biodegradable wastes (Domingo & Manoos, 2017). On the other hand, uncontrolled burning in the backyard is a bad practice for reducing biodegradable waste because it causes premature deaths in adults due to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (Reyna-Bensusan et al., 2018).

Non-biodegradable waste. Parkar et al. (2021) described non-biodegradable waste as a waste that does not break down when exposed to the action of microorganisms. Some examples of non-biodegradable wastes include plastic, rubber, metal waste containers, and other types of packaging. Furthermore, their findings also stipulate that plastic has become a vital component of daily life because of its adaptability, leading to various uses. However, because it is not biodegradable, the issue occurs when it does not break down in the natural environment. Therefore, it is essential to minimize the use of plastic whenever possible. Plastics can either be recycled or utilized to reach this goal.

The same was also confirmed in the study of Dwivedi et al. (2019), which points out that materials like polymers play a crucial role in our daily tasks. Due to their wide range of applications across numerous industries, polymers have consequently seen a tremendous expansion in global production and disposal. However, a considerable portion of the polymeric wastes do not decompose and are bulkier than the organic

remains. Because of this, non-biodegradable polymeric waste has accumulated due to their constant demand, taking up a lot of landfill space and posing environmental risks.

Accordingly, the findings of Domingo and Manos (2017) disclosed that the coastal people of Boac, Marinduque, Philippines, sort their wastes by separating biodegradable and non-biodegradable, dumping them in vacant lots, and recycling them. However, most of their research respondents prefer trading some of the non-biodegradable wastes in junk shops rather than recycling.

Hazardous waste. Wastes classified as hazardous have characteristics that make them unsafe or potentially damaging to the environment or human health. Liquid, solid, confined gas, and sludge are all examples of hazardous wastes.

As emphasized by Narayan et al. (2022), hazardous healthcare waste generated in the homes of the Coastal City of Karnataka, India, makes up about 0.5 percent of biomedical waste. It is frequently thrown away with other household garbage, although it may be contagious. Their study indicated that baby diapers were the most prevalent hazardous trash. Likewise, there is more generation of other sanitary wastes such as used condoms, particles from menstruation, razor blades, and lancets monthly. Compared to rural families, 28 (37.33 percent) of urban households had higher knowledge of potentially hazardous healthcare waste than 7 (9.3 percent) of them. A majority of households—71 (94.7 percent) in urban areas and 49 (65.3 percent) in rural areas—were in support of disposing hazardous home biological waste. Comparatively, urban households show better knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding hazardous healthcare waste created at the household level.

At a Zimbabwean university, Maphosa (2021) investigated students' awareness and attitude toward e-waste management practices. The paper describes complicated problems associated with incorrect e-waste treatment in a developing nation, which leads to deterioration of the environment and human health. An electronic survey was used to collect data from 216 student respondents. According to the findings, majority of participants disposed of their e-waste with regular trash. To ensure proper management of e-waste, participants highlighted the need for greater awareness, policies, collection sites, and recycling services. Effective e-waste management practices have not been implemented despite knowledge of the harm that e-waste causes to the environment and to people's health. The research calls on policymakers to create e-waste rules and value chains that will sustain the e-waste ecosystem. The institution should set up key recycling facilities, establish e-waste collection stations, and create local e-waste rules. Establishing e-waste societies within the university would help to spread awareness, education, and a pro-environment attitude towards managing electronic waste.

The results are likewise evident in the study of Celestial et al. (2018) on "Management of E-waste in the Philippines referred to "E-waste" as outdated or discarded electrical equipment. E-waste handling that is improper or outdated may emit toxic byproducts that are bad for the environment and human health. They disclosed that official statistics on generation of e-waste in the Philippines are lacking. To create a

database and evaluation system for managing electronic waste, the government can work with academic institutions, facilities that process e-waste, civic society, and other organizations. On that account, they asserted that the national and municipal governments should implement and execute existing e-waste rules including the Basel Convention, RA 6969 and 9003, and DAO 2013-22 more strictly. Lastly, they contended that public awareness of e-waste risks and management is necessary, including information on accredited E-waste Treatment, Storage, and Disposal (TSD) facilities.

Act of 2000 on Management of Ecological Solid Waste Management (RA 9003). The Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000, also known as Republic Act 9003, was passed on January 26, 2001 in the Philippines in response to the growing problems with solid waste management (Atienza, 2020). According to RA 9003, the field of the management of solid waste is focused on the production, preservation, transfer, gathering, and transfer of solid wastes as well as their processing and disposal (Ibañez & Torrentira, 2022).

Specifically, in response to the urgent demand for solid waste management and the threat it poses to the environment and human health, former President Gloria Macapagal-Arroyo approved the Ecological Solid Waste Management Act in the year 2000. This RA 9003 mandates that every LGU turns its uncontrolled dumps into controlled ones for a period of three (3) years of its approval and that no dumps that are controlled shall be allowed for five (5) years following the Act's implementation. In addition, Section 10 specifies the role of LGUs in the management of solid waste, wherein sorting as well as collecting of solid waste, especially biodegradable, compostable, and reusable waste should be done at the barangay level, provided that the municipality or city is in charge of collecting materials that cannot be recycled and other types of waste (Dalugdog, 2021).

Recently, Ibañez and Torrentira (2022) emphasized in their study that waste management has an impact on the environment and public health. Management of Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) is challenging in emerging and developed countries. They also reported that solid waste from generation to final disposal in Tanauan, Leyte could be categorized into five functional parts: (1) trash generation, (2) trash storage, (3) trash collection, (4) trash transportation, and (5) trash disposal. Residents in their own homes do the first two things, while Tanauan's local government does the last three. Furthermore, the rapid population development and economic growth are environmentally-damaging and have affected how people make and categorize waste. They also stressed that people in impoverished countries are not very good at handling municipal solid trash, which has caused an issue. While developing nations produce less solid waste, improper disposal pollutes the environment. Lack of knowledge in waste management contributes to environmental issues. This led to the passing of the Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000 (RA 9003).

Furthermore, Formarejo and colleagues' (2022) correlational study reported that Inland resorts have a high degree of awareness of Republic Act 9003, actively participate in it, have a lot of resources at their disposal, and strictly enforce and follow it. They also came to the conclusion that public participation is closely tied to understanding, supplies,

and execution. Enforcement is moderately connected with resource availability and public awareness but immensely associated with participation and resources. Compliance to RA 9003 is connected with resources and enforcement but not with involvement and awareness. RA 9003 compliance is not, however, predicted by factors like awareness, involvement, resources, or enforcement. Accordingly, Republic Act 9003 is a good law, but Senator Loren Legarda stressed that its effective implementation depends on everyone's efforts. In particular, the LGUs and barangays with the authority to implement and enforce the law should ensure strict compliance with this law's mandatory requirements.

Romualdo et al. (2022) conducted a study to evaluate the degree of implementation and integration of solid waste management indicators in General Santos's public and private schools in terms of reuse, reduction, collection, recycling, treatment, and final disposal of waste, and IEC drive. The respondents, which included students in senior high school, teachers in science, and school administrators from one (1) public and one (1) private school, were given a modified questionnaire. The comparison of execution and integration outcomes between private and public educational institutions revealed that both substantially executed and integrated the solid waste management policy, with respective composite means of 3.55 and 3.42. With a t-value of 1.03941 and a p-value of 0.319106, which is less than 0.05 (p.05), the results of the T-test on the degree of Solid Waste Management execution and integration between the two chosen big institutions in General Santos City revealed no significant difference. This explains why General Santos City's two public and private schools implement and integrate solid waste management considerably. Therefore, it is essential that schools continue giving solid waste management programs and causes top priority. The administrators of the schools must also uphold high standards for the inclusion of SWM in the educational process through initiatives, rewards, alliances, collaborations, organizational resources, and equity.

Problems on solid waste management. Khalid and colleagues (2022) stressed that disposal of waste is among the most serious issues in the environment. Air, water, and soil contamination caused by poor management of waste change the ecosystem, and threatens human health. In fact, local people who lived near Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) plants had babies with low birth weights, birth defects, and a small number of cancers when they were young. Furthermore, the increased production of solid wastes intensified the increasing costs of municipal budgets. Due to improving standards of living, urbanization, economic growth, and population growth, municipal solid waste production has noticeably expanded. This section will discuss the various problems on solid waste management according to the following: 1) insufficient sorting of SW, 2) low awareness of SWM, 3) poor dumping practices, 4) poor coordination on proper SWM, and 5) attitude.

Insufficient sorting of SW. The study of Coracero et al. (2021) includes the release of the press from the Senate Economic Planning Office (SEPO) in 2017 containing a presentation in tabular form of the daily generation of solid waste in tons according to an article from National Solid Waste Management Commission (NSWMC). The tabular presentation displays daily generation of waste by region from year 2012 to

year 2016. The production in the Philippines increased from 37,427.46 tons in year 2012 to 40,087.45 tons in year 2016. It was discovered that NCR, Region 4A (Calabarzon), and Region 3 (Central Luzon) were among the most significant sources of production of solid waste in Luzon. The aforesaid regions produced 1,754,241 tons of solid trash in 2016, accounting for 43.76 percent of nation's total waste. Enormously populated communities were dispersed throughout the said regions, particularly the NCR, where Manila, the Philippine capital, can be found. As stated in their report, the quantity of generated waste in Philippine cities increases by approximately 165% by year 2025, from 29,315 to 77,776 tons per day. Increased waste production is seen to be one of the main reasons of problems with solid waste management, such as a lack of space for trash disposal.

According to Nguyen and Tan (2020), most waste management studies in rural regions revealed a lack of local policies. For example, with the solid waste management (SWM) ordinance not yet in effect, Barangay Lahug in Cebu City approved the "No Segregation, No Collection" policy for the entire city. Another is the absence of Materials Recovery Facilities (MRFs) and unsegregated wastes in Bayog, Los Baños, and Laguna, which indicate that RA 9003 has not been implemented there. Furthermore, biodegradable waste composting was minimally practiced. Instead, kitchen scraps were either fed to domestic animals or dumped outside the home. Thus, the strict waste management regulations put in place by the local municipal government were followed by every village.

The inappropriate disposal of solid waste may lead to unsanitary conditions and environmental contamination. It can also cause Vector-borne disease outbreaks. If solid waste is not sorted correctly, it can harm our health, environment, and prosperity. Ineffective solid waste management pollutes the world's oceans, clogging sewers and causing flooding (Ijjasz-Vasquez et al., 2018).

Low awareness of SWM. The study of Domingo and Manoos (2017) exposed that the responses of the residents in Boac, Marinduque in anticipating any problems with the solid waste management they currently practice are "high." However, some residents expressed that they do not expect any problems with the solid waste management they currently practice. Furthermore, the practices and problems encountered by residents revealed that most of them have an equal amount of biodegradable and non-biodegradable waste they produce daily from their routine demands. Most barangays separated their biodegradable from non-biodegradable waste before disposal, while others did not practice waste segregation. Lastly, the data on the respondents' degree of knowledge regarding solid waste management laws in their municipality and barangay displays that most responses are "I know, but I do not fully comprehend." It demonstrates that they are aware of the meaning and objectives but are not fully aware of them. In summary, their findings suggested that if the residents' practices are low, the higher the problems are encountered by the residents regarding waste management.

The same is likewise evident in the study of Saguban (2020), where residents' level of involvement and awareness of programs for proper management of solid waste

in a specific barangay is only "high." Next, she also noted that the residents practice waste segregation, but their performance is "not very high." She made emphasis that the local governments blamed waste generators' lack of awareness and discipline for poor segregation. In terms of composting biodegradable wastes, the extent of application by residents only shows "moderately high." Such a result would mean the conduct of training for the barangay residents concerning composting is not fully observed. Lastly, Application of solid waste management procedures varies significantly between barangay officials and residents. In summary, her findings revealed that if the extent of solid waste management practices is highly applied or implemented, the lower are the problems encountered in solid waste management.

However, in the study of Bungau et al. (2018) on pharmaceutical waste management in Romania, their findings showed that pharmacy professionals are unconcerned and poorly informed about the utilization and disposal of pharmaceutical waste. More informational initiatives are therefore necessary to update and teach the general public on the safe handling, storage, and disposal of medical waste. Furthermore, the results of their survey also showed that the lengthy process/lack of time, lack of legislation/method of collection, lack of processes, and expensive expenses are the primary reasons why some pharmacists refuse to accept unused prescriptions from the general population. Specific and comprehensive legislation is needed to address these issues, as well as the public's lack of interest, inadequate knowledge about decreasing pharmaceutical waste, and rising medication consumption. Clear roles, duties and education/awareness campaigns for employees and citizens must be included in laws, policies, and procedures for recovering pharmaceutical waste from the general population.

The same was also confirmed in the study of Parajuly et al. (2020) on electronic waste management. Environmental problems such as municipal solid waste management are rooted in human behavior and behavioral changes. Environmental literacy does not translate into sustainable actions. As a result, the effectiveness of intervention strategies to encourage pro-environmental behavior relying on information campaigns is limited. Moreover, beliefs about environmental impacts and the effectiveness of one's action come into play between values and norms. In other words, these beliefs and norms, and thus the willingness to perform a particular action, can be shaped by information.

Poor dumping practices. Different forms of municipal solid waste could affect human health and the environment depending on garbage disposal practices. In fact, plastic wastes are an increasing source of worry globally since they linger for long periods. If organisms ingest plastic wastes, this may impact the health of the food chain, including humans. Moreover, fugitive emissions from waste treatments were responsible for 3%–4% of the world's greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions back in 2006. Another significant long-term local effect of waste leachate's nitrogen pollution is the possibility of disease and nutrient imbalances in neighboring water bodies. Lastly, the open burning of wastes produces substantial amounts of dangerous air pollutants that could seriously harm the human health particularly in developing countries (Chen et al., 2020).

In a book written by Kaza et al. (2018), it was stressed that poorly managed waste contaminates the world's oceans, clogs sewers and causes flooding, transmits diseases by vector breeding, increases respiratory problems from burning waste, harms animals that unintentionally consume waste, and affects economic development. Waste from decades of economic progress needs immediate response at all levels of society. Furthermore, based on waste volume, composition, and management, solid waste treatment and disposal produced 1.6 billion tons of carbon dioxide (CO₂) equivalent greenhouse gas emissions, primarily from open dumping and landfills without landfill gas capture systems. In fact, there is 5 percent of worldwide gas emissions. If no changes are made, solid waste-related CO₂ emissions might reach 2.6 billion tons annually by 2050.

The same is likewise evident in the study of Domingo and Manoos (2017), that in most households in barangays where garbage is not collected, the residents dispose their waste improperly by burning, burying, or tossing it into adjacent creeks, vacant lots, and open canals, or the coastline. As an outcome, the shorelines frequently have waste and trash during rainy seasons. Furthermore, dumping in vacant lots results in an insect breeding ground, an eyesore to the general public, production of unpleasant smells, high winds and floods spread solid waste, and waste scattered by animals. Meanwhile, the direct burning of waste produces dense smoke and an unpleasant smell which can harm or aggravate the health of persons with cardiac conditions and impair the environment. Lastly, dumping solid waste in rivers, streams, and oceans in the coastal barangays causes terrible odor and water pollution and hinders fishing and other water activities.

As stressed by Gelan (2021), without any sorting, the collected trash from Addis Abeba, Ethiopia, is dumped at the Reppi open landfill site. Open dumping, according to him, is by far the most typical practice. Hence, this type of waste disposal practice will cause problems for the community and the environment. In addition, he also conveyed that there is a lack of segregation practices in the waste dump that encourages many salvages (waste pickers) to enter and search the area for recyclable and reusable products. The landfill has also caused various societal problems, such as odor and environmental issues. In summary, his findings stipulated that if the waste segregation practices are low, the higher are the problems encountered in waste management.

Poor coordination on proper SWM. Meanwhile, the study of Gelan (2021) revealed that an organization is in charge of regulating the transportation and dumping of solid garbage from districts and sub-cities. The organization's main tasks included gathering solid waste generated on the street and moving collected solid waste to the landfill. To manage the trash produced by various service providers (Non-Governmental Organizations and the business sector) and families, the organization has offered transportation and solid waste collection services to private groups. Unfortunately, these groups' services are insufficient to collect the waste produced in the city entirely. He also mentioned how cities in developing nations have not been able to implement Integrated Solid Waste Management (ISWM) systems fully.

The same finding was also revealed in the study of Saguban (2020), where standard collection vehicles used are open dump trucks and compactor trucks. The

poorer areas of cities, municipalities, and rural barangays are typically under-served. As a result, the uncollected trash primarily winds up in neighboring water bodies, which pollutes the major water bodies as well as clogs the drainage systems, and causes flooding during heavy rains. In addition, her findings also revealed that the problems encountered by the barangays have a significant relationship and inverse relationship, although weak, with the following SWM practices in terms of the extent of application, such as the creation of 1) barangay solid waste management committee; 2) no segregation, no collection policy; 3) promotion of reducing, reusing, and recycling (3Rs); and 4) Collection and disposal of solid wastes.

Consequently, the problems encountered by the barangays have no significant relationship to the following extent of application of SWM practices such as 1) promotion of composting of biodegradable wastes and 2) the establishment of the material recovery facility. Lastly, the results indicated a significant but weak relationship between the problems encountered in maintaining solid garbage disposal and the degree of involvement of the community in formulation and implementation.

Attitude. The study of Wu et al. (2021) reported that as urbanization has accelerated, municipal solid waste (MSW) has risen dramatically. China has enacted a mandatory classification policy for municipal solid waste to recycle MSW more efficiently. Moreover, public MSW sorting behavior is significantly affected by attitude. Their study analyzed the data of Sina Weibo users and their remarks on related popular posts to examine the emotional disposition of Chinese residents toward the MSW sorting policy. In the interim, text-mining technology was utilized to examine the result. Although a significant fraction of the Chinese population shows a positive attitude toward the municipal solid waste (MSW) sorting policy, the ratio of individuals with a negative attitude reached nearly half. In addition, different regions of China give varying amounts of attention to the MSW sorting policy. In addition, the results revealed that penalties, MSW sorting rules, fees, the timing of waste disposal, and irregular recycling procedures were the primary causes of the public's negative attitude. Lastly, their study provides policy guidance for practitioners and policymakers by analyzing public sentiment regarding sorting municipal solid waste (MSW).

Solid waste management practices. Currently, the majority of waste is dumped or disposed of in a landfill of some kind. A landfill is used to dispose about 37 percent of waste, and 8 percent of that waste is dumped in sanitary landfills with landfill gas collection systems. Thirty-three percent of waste is dumped openly, nineteen percent is recycled or composted, and eleven percent is burned as the last step in the disposal (Kaza et al., 2018). This section will discuss the various solid waste management practices according to the following 7R's: 1) rethink, 2) refuse, 3) reduce, 4) reuse, 5) repair, 6) regift, and 7) recycle.

Rethink. According to Los Angeles County Public Works (2023), future generations would benefit from a more sustainable environment if people minimize waste production. Rethink before discarding an item that is believed to be damaged, worn out, or no longer desired. Before discarding anything, one should consider if the item can be

reused, repaired, or recycled. In addition, Abdullah's book (2021) emphasizes that the 'rethink' principle for consumers may entail an understanding of how to properly dispose of used items properly, whereas, for manufacturers, it entails the creation of environmentally friendly products. Innovative new products should include eco-friendly antibacterial face masks, biodegradable mitts, and compostable shields. As is customary in the business world, the most crucial factor is that manufacturers make all these products accessible to consumers from diverse economic circumstances. Producing high-quality products at affordable prices is a challenge. Still, it is the duty and responsibility of manufacturers to consider it, following the demand to rethink for the sake of the environment.

The study of M'Nkubitu (2022) on rethinking organic municipal solid waste management in Kenyan urban areas emphasized that organic waste makes up a significant portion of municipal solid waste, particularly in developing nations. Its management faces numerous obstacles, ranging from limited financial and technical resources to a lack of or ineffective policy enforcement. As a result, such factors lead to improper waste management, leading to open dumping and disposal in landfills if the 7Rs' rethink principle is not practiced. These practices are detrimental to both the environment and the human population. Actors in various locations have implemented circular economy strategies to manage organic waste better and recover resources to improve the situation.

In addition, Akala (2021) emphasized that Kakamega County lacked knowledge on fitting the 7Rs strategy (reduction, rethinking, refusal, recycling, reusing, repairing, and refilling) to the generated banana waste; banana waste utilization technologies; and challenges of on-farm banana waste management. The findings of their study showed that 75% of farmers had embraced and disregarded the 7Rs' rethink in banana waste business incubation, innovation, and diffusion of banana waste utilization and management strategies in equal proportion.

Moreover, the study of Ibañez and Torrentira (2022) asserted that "limited" information and education campaigns result in poor waste segregation practices at the household level of Tanauan, Leyte. For this reason, the 7Rs in terms of rethink is not well practiced because each household collected their wastes in a single container, wherein biodegradables, non-biodegradables, and all other wastes were mixed because people did not bother to segregate them. The municipality does not currently have a policy or local regulation encouraging residents to practice waste segregation. Furthermore, there are no specific schedules or trucks designated to collect various types of waste during waste collection.

Furthermore, it was accentuated in the study of Tupas and Cacho (2020) that the number of households in Northern Ilo-ilo and their status significantly affect the amount of trash they make. Therefore, an education campaign by the LGUs can help people learn to practice the 7Rs – rethink to get rid of waste in a way that is good for the environment and their health. For a successful implementation of solid waste management, there must be political will and commitment.

Refuse. Reegan (2023) noted that the 7Rs' refuse is likewise described as considering before purchasing or not at all. Consumers will likely buy fewer items that cause the least environmental damage. In addition, Abdullah stated that 'refuse' means evading extravagance or refraining from unnecessary buying. In this connection, Rebullida and Taguibao (2020) emphasized that one of the principles of the 7Rs is refuse, which means to consider the purchase of items if unnecessary or excessive. Several city societies, non-government organizations, and local government units must advocate for this 7Rs practice to decrease the problems such as dumping in landfills and open dump sites, which can cause environmental degradation. The same is likewise stated in the study of Govani et al. (2021) on new-generation technologies for solid waste management. They emphasized that refusing is the second thing people can do after rethinking. Buying essential products is unavoidable, but people can refuse to purchase items with over-packaging or decorations to minimize waste.

Moreover, the study of Akala (2021) stressed that the 7Rs' refuse could be utilized as one of the waste management strategies to transform banana waste into an economic resource. However, more is needed to know why applying 7Rs to banana waste remains minimal. Thus, invoking disposal as a banana waste management strategy is retrogressive and perpetuates environmental degradation, and retard the welfare of Kenyan banana farmers.

Meanwhile, the findings of Tupas and Cacho (2020) acknowledged that a robust waste management program that is run well is good for the environment and people's health. For example, plastics are being banned in almost all cities and towns in Northern Ilo-ilo. Eco-friendly materials are being used instead. People are informed to bring their own bags to the market to practice the 7Rs' refuse principle. On the other hand, Bagui and Arellano (2021) noted that the anti-plastic ordinance in Batangas City says people cannot use plastic or Styrofoam. However, the ordinance has no cooperation and is not strictly observed enough among the people.

Reduce. Accordingly, Abdullah (2021) stated that the "reduce" principle calls for reusable products and a reduction in the number of utilized resources such as water and energy. Moreover, Reegan (2023) noted that some practices under the 7Rs' reduce principle include buying less, purchasing products with minimal or no packaging that lasts a long time, and borrowing instead of purchasing, donating, or selling unwanted items at home. In this connection, the study by Khalid, Ullah, and Umar (2022), they pointed out that traditional landfill, incineration, composting, and other practices are used for reducing solid waste. The most common approaches to reduce waste materials are treating and using the organic component of municipal solid waste in the past, have been anaerobic digestion and composting.

Tavill (2020) defined food waste as uneaten edible food primarily generated at the consumer level, either at or away from home. Given how complicated society is regarding food preferences, practices, and consumer awareness, it may be hard to reduce waste at home without help from technology and industry. From that point of view, companies

are already finding ways to store, preserve, and process food and improve packaging technology. Aside from how products are made, the industry can support technology to help consumers reduce food waste. For example, "connected homes" that use mobile apps, smart appliances, and e-commerce platforms are utilized to help with planning, inventory management, and cooking techniques can help reduce food waste at the consumer level.

Furthermore, the study of Mihai and Ingrao (2018) pointed out that proper management of bio-waste, which makes up the majority of municipal waste, is the key to sustaining a bio-economy in the near future. The amount of uncollected bio-waste by waste collectors is usually thrown away without control if it is not recovered through home composting as a means of waste reduction. Thus, home composting plays a crucial role in reducing the bio-waste losses through waste dumping across rural Romania.

Reuse. According to Los Angeles County Public Works (2023), the 7Rs' reuse can be readily implemented by repeatedly reusing an item. In other words, people can frequently reuse items for the same purpose. With enough creativity, they can also serve a new function. Some observable practices under this principle include bringing reusable bags when shopping, returning disposable bags to the grocery for recycling, using egg cartons to sprout seedlings before transplanting, reusing glass jars to store extra sauce or liquid, and reusing peanut butter or mayonnaise jars to store homemade cookies. In this connection, Abdullah (2021) stressed that people can apply the 'reuse' principle by using single items until they are worn out, as long as they are safe to use. He further added that 'reuse' is transferring a used product in good condition to another user, such as through a second-hand marketplace. It can help manufacturers by allowing them to maintain the quality of their equipment. At the same time, consumers get a low-cost and well-maintained used product. Practicing this principle will also save the environment by minimizing waste.

Moreover, farmers also practiced the reuse principle in Akala's (2021) study regarding managing banana waste. Occasionally, containers and sacks have been reused for grain and water storage without adequate sanitation, endangering crops, livestock, and human health and life. In addition, the reuse of banana waste was instrumental in establishing and maintaining vegetable, fruit, and tree nursery beds, which could benefit the horticultural industry.

Accordingly, the study of Park and Tucker (2017) explained the issues facing stakeholders regarding the reuse of construction waste in Australia. Their findings reveal that institutional barriers are caused by problems outside the construction industry, such as social, economic, and political barriers to change. Factors such as lack of interest and demand from clients, attitudes towards reuse practices, and training make it hard to use construction wastes proactively and sustainably. Above all, they argued that laws should be implemented better to ensure that all Australian states are required to reuse construction waste materials.

Repair. The 7 R's also include the word repair, which encourages people to restore items rather than discard and replace them. Almost always, repair is less expensive than purchasing new products with the same utility. This may entail sewing a button onto a blouse or repairing a bicycle so that a person can ride to work instead of driving. People tend to discard "broken" products without attempting to find a solution to restore their functionality (Anderson, 2021). Accordingly, Reegan (2023) emphasized that repair, as one of the 7Rs' principles, entails attempting to restore items before throwing them away. The common culture instilled in most of the human populace is labeled a "throwaway society" because more waste is in landfills. Discarding items that have the potential to be reused and recycled would harm the environment and requires more natural resources to reproduce new products. By participating in the "Repair Movement" and repairing objects, people can help conserve the planet's resources.

Abdullah (2021) also added that the 'repair' principle allows manufacturers to keep and use products for a much longer period of time. The "repair" principle also applies to consumers who own a product and keep it in good condition. These measures save money and benefit the environment in the long run. Furthermore, Bateman, Whiting, and Shine (2022) confirmed that it is essential to repair electronic devices. According to the article he wrote, a circular vision for the electronic waste sector will support the elimination of waste and it could generate up to \$4.5 trillion in economic benefits by 2030. The article also emphasized that changing how people consume is fundamental to the solution and should be a top priority. In addition, they discovered that prolonging the lifespan of a smartphone from 2.5 years to 7 years results in carbon dioxide equivalent savings of approximately 100 kilograms.

Regift. The study by Gates and Wu (2018) highlighted that regifting is the concept of donating a gift or item you have received to a family member/friend or a charity. Regifting has many advantages, including reducing clutter, giving an item "a second chance," and assisting the environment by reducing waste. Like minimalism, veganism, and waste-free lifestyles, regifting has become environmentally responsible, sustainable, and increasingly popular. Creating a regifting store will not only simplify the process of regifting, but it will also generate funds for a worthy charity, such as St. Gabriel's School and Centre. At the same time, practicing this 7Rs' regift will help reduce environmental waste. The longevity and popularity of the concept will ensure this store's continued relevance and prosperity in the future.

Taylor and Street's (2023) study revealed that the high adoption of gifting is likely due to the Buy Nothing Project (BNP) organizations' product reuse convenience. Many also cited concern for the traditional pathways for product reuse in Australia as a reason for using the groups: two participants suggested that they are attempting to reduce the burden of solid waste on charity shops, and another remarked that "donating to a charity store can be a bit of a hassle at times." The BNP groups represent a potential remedy for the nonprofit sector's current economic and logistical constraints. Gifting also has emotional value for members, who are frequently more concerned that cherished but no longer needed items to find a "good home" and trust their neighbors to do so. Members also mentioned regifting things they had received from the group when their need for them

had passed. Thus, items may have multiple uses within the community. Frequently, the organizations are utilized to promote skills and educate regarding repurposing and recycling. One participant remarked that even damaged or torn items are taken and that they can observe "how people refashion things" or use items they would never have considered reusable.

Regift is one of the 7R's where giving a previously received gift to another person, sometimes under the pretense of a new gift is practiced. Regifting unused items instead of discarding them is advantageous for the environment because it reduces waste. Regifting also allows people to dispose of unwanted gifts by donating them to others. Recycling is commonly associated with disassembling and reassembling components into new products (Wikipedia, 2023). Moreover, Hyundai (2023) noted that "regifting" is giving another individual a previously loved pre-owned item to increase its value. It is one of 7R's practical concepts because it prevents items from being discarded in the trash. As "regifts," clothing, shoes, furniture, and electronic devices may be donated to charitable organizations. One can regift books and other items with sentimental value to members of your family and friends by wrapping and presenting them to loved ones.

Recycle. Reagan (2023) noted some observable recycling practices, such as reusing things back into the waste stream for something else, recycling used glass in road construction, melting plastics to make new products, and composting organic waste as fertilizers in the gardens. Accordingly, Tan, Ying, and Hamid (2021) noted that some types of single-use plastic wastes are nonclinical or nonhazardous and made from thermoplastic, such as polypropylene, and hence, the principle of 7Rs' recycling can be practiced. The findings of Chinchodkar and Jadhav (2018) revealed that 51% of urban MSW in India is organic matter, 18% is only recyclable of the MSW, and the rest is 31% inert waste. Among the various types of waste treatment methods, biodegradable, material recycling, and waste-to-energy (WTE) facilities are recognized as promising alternatives to overcome the waste generation problem and a potential source for reduction, revenue, reuse, and renewable energy.

Moreover, Coracero, Gallego, Frago, and Gonzales (2021) emphasized that RA 9003 (Ecological Solid Waste Management Act) mandates collecting only segregated waste. There shall be compostable, recyclable, non-recyclable, and remarkable waste-labeled containers. People are encouraged to create compost from waste to be used as fertilizer. They believe the solution to waste problems will begin at home. In effect, individuals who properly segregate could separate recyclables and other materials. Furthermore, the municipal waste collectors in Manila are responsible for disposing between 47.25 and 74.85 percent of their total recyclable wastes. In Metro Cebu, more households sold/gave recyclable wastes to door-to-door collectors, spanning between 27.88% and 64.86 % of the total recyclable wastes. In addition, homes in Southern Mindanao prioritized door-to-door collectors, with percentages ranging from 9.51 to 51.69 percent of their complete recyclable wastes. It can be seen that recycling centers had the lowest rate of being a priority for recyclable waste disposal. Recycling centers are better equipped to utilize this waste than municipal collectors.

Solid waste management based on demographic profile. This section of the paper discusses the different findings on problems and practices in waste management based on the demographic profile in terms of 1) age, 2) sex, 3) educational attainment of parents, and 4) family monthly income.

On age. Madrigal and Oracion (2017) emphasized that awareness, attitudes, and practices towards solid waste management were significantly related to age. This result, however, contradicted the results of Miner et al.'s (2020) study in Nigeria, indicating no correlation between the respondents' ages and their awareness levels of e-waste management and intention to participate. Meanwhile, in the study of Douthett et al. (2017) on solid waste management challenges in urban areas of Ghana, their data demonstrated that most of their research respondents who encounter problems with household waste belong to the middle age groups from 41 to 50 years old.

Furthermore, Escario, Rodriguez-Sanchez, and Casaló (2020) highlighted in their study that age has something to do with the environmental attitudes and perceived effectiveness of recycling, reducing, and reusing (3Rs). They reported that Spanish residents aged over 17 years show a positive relationship between environmental attitudes and the five waste-related behaviors. Hence, a positive relationship between the perceived effectiveness of one's behavior (when nobody else acts pro-environmentally) and the five waste-related behaviors is also evident. The same was likewise affirmed in the study of Choon, Tan, and Chong (2017) on the perception of households about solid waste management issues in Malaysia. Their findings revealed a positive relationship between age and waste reduction behaviors. Their respondents confirmed that their lifestyle affected waste reduction. Almost half of the respondents responded that they lacked the knowledge to practice waste segregation.

However, the study of Laor et al. (2018) on the knowledge, attitude, and practice of municipal solid waste management among highland residents in Northern Thailand exposed that the issue must target young people less than 20 years old. This target group must obtain adequate knowledge and education on municipal solid waste management, which impacts their health and hygiene. Hence, the local government should prioritize these individuals to encourage knowledge acquisition and a positive attitude toward effective municipal solid waste management. Lastly, information campaigns on waste management and appropriate media are necessary for the target group.

On sex. The findings of Madrigal and Oracion (2017) also noted that sex showed no correlation with attitude or practice towards solid waste management. This result affirmed the statement of Miner et al.'s (2020) findings where it indicates no correlation between the respondents' sex and their awareness of e-waste management and intention to participate.

Furthermore, Douthett et al. (2017) also noted that more women directly encounter household waste problems than men. The authors argue that their findings are consistent with the research established in solid waste management because they believe that women play a vital role in maintaining the household. Moreover, they also remarked that

household waste management is a woman's job in these countries because they are directly concerned with household chores.

The same was also substantiated in the study of Escario, Rodriguez-Sanchez, and Casaló (2020). They noted that sex has something to do with the environmental attitudes and perceived effectiveness of recycling, reducing, and reusing (3Rs). Regarding sociodemographic characteristics, their findings reveal that women engage more in these 3R behaviors. However, they emphasized that women exhibit more significant reducing and reusing but not recycling behaviors compared to men. Lastly, Laor et al. (2018) also reveal that females display a more positive attitude in practicing municipal solid waste management than males.

On educational attainment of parents. As Madrigal and Oracion (2017) emphasized, awareness, attitudes, and practices toward solid waste management were significantly related to educational level. Lim et al. (2017), observed that the 3Rs gap in action and practices on solid waste management is due to the residents' lack of education and awareness. According to Janmaimool (2017), people with bachelor's degree encounter problems in sustainable waste management than those with master's degree levels. The same is likewise evident in the study of Escario, Rodriguez-Sanchez, and Casaló (2020) as they articulated that highly educated people engage more in these 3R behaviors. It was also validated in the study of Choon, Tan, and Chong (2017), where they found that education level positively correlates to reuse and recycling behaviors.

On the contrary, a study conducted by Saguban (2020) found that educated or professional inhabitants made up most of those who engaged in improper waste disposal practice.

Meanwhile a study of Miner et al. (2020), reveals that there is no correlation between the respondents' current educational level and intention to participate in e-waste management. Similar findings was found in the study of Laor et al. (2018) which reveal that most respondents, regardless of their educational level, show a neutral attitude toward SW Management.

Family monthly income. The analysis of Chen, Bodirsky, Krueger, Mishra, and Popp (2020) suggested that richer developed countries continue to produce the most waste. This is due to the reason that per capita waste production and income are correlated. They predict that waste production will continue to increase and that unsustainable ways of dealing with waste, like putting it in landfills, will continue to dominate. The study of Nagpure (2019) underscored that per capita, illegally dumped municipal solid waste was found to be highest in the low socioeconomic status (61 kg), followed by middle socioeconomic status (4 kg) and high socioeconomic status (2.6–3.5 kg) neighborhoods. In summary, it was shown in his findings that households with a low socioeconomic status (SES) have the highest municipal solid waste (MSW) contribution, which leads to serious environmental problems.

Meanwhile, Kaza, Yao, Bhada-Tata, and Van Woerden (2018) noted that 3.40 billion tons of trash will be produced worldwide by the year 2050. They further claimed that generation of waste and income level generally have a positive correlation.

Accordingly, the findings of Madrigal and Oracion (2017) depicted a significant difference in knowledge, attitude, and behaviors in waste management in grouping students according to family background, religion, and monthly income. In the study of Saguban (2020), the results revealed that residents who are those in the middle-class level of economic status have poor waste segregation practices. The preceding results, however, contradicted the study of Miner et al. (2020), where their findings displayed no correlation between the respondents' family size, family income, marital status, and their current educational level and intention to participate in e-waste management.

Research Questions

The study aimed to identify the problems and practices in solid waste management of students at home.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following specific questions:

1. To what extent are the problems encountered by the students on solid waste management at home in terms of the following:
 - 1.1 insufficient sorting of SW;
 - 1.2 low awareness of proper SWM;
 - 1.3 poor dumping practices;
 - 1.4 poor coordination on proper SWM; and
 - 1.5 attitude?
2. To what extent are the practices of the students on solid waste management in terms of the 7R's (rethink, refuse, reduce, reuse, repair, regift, and recycle)?
3. Is there a significant relationship between problems and practices in solid waste management of students?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the students (age, sex, educational attainment of parents, and family monthly income) and the following:
 - 4.1 practices; and
 - 4.2 problems encountered?

Statement of the Null Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between problems and practices in solid waste management of students.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between the profile of the students (age, sex, educational attainment of parents, and family monthly income) and the practices and problems encountered.

METHODOLOGY

Research design. The research utilized the descriptive-correlational survey. It is descriptive because it (a) identified the practices and problems encountered by students on waste management at home, (b) described the profile of the students, and (c) evaluated the outcomes of the practices of students on waste management at home. On the other hand, it is also correlational because the mentioned variables were correlated.

Research environment. The study was conducted at Negros Oriental State University (NORSU)–Pamplona Extension Campus at Sitio Tuwang, Barangay Poblacion, Municipality of Pamplona, Negros Oriental. NORSU is a public institution and one of the most prominent state universities with several satellite and extension campuses in Negros Oriental province. The Pamplona extension only offers the programs Bachelor of Science in Agriculture majors in Animal Science and Agronomy and Bachelor of Science in Forestry, respectively. The BS Agriculture and BS Forestry students came from urban, semi-urban, and rural areas. Hence, the data gathered were based on the respondents' perception of how they managed their waste at home.

Research respondents. The respondents of the study were the randomly selected first-year to fourth-year students from NORSU – Pamplona Extension. Of the 369 total population of the extension campus, only 169 students were considered as part of the study.

Course Program	Population	Sample
BS Agriculture	281	136
BS Forestry	<u>88</u>	<u>33</u>
	369	169

In identifying the sample respondents, the systematic sampling technique was used wherein every second student in the list was chosen as the respondents.

Research instruments. The study used a researcher-made questionnaire to determine the problems and practices of students in solid waste management at home. The questionnaire is composed of three parts.

Part I asked for the profile of the students according to age, sex, educational attainment of the parents, and family monthly income. Part II consisted of areas with corresponding indicators which determined the extent of problems encountered on solid waste management. Meanwhile, Part III determined the extent of practices on solid waste management. The researchers also read articles and publications regarding solid waste management in schools and the community and integrated significant items into the questionnaire.

The whole questionnaire was presented to three experts in the field of science for content validity and cross-checking if the items were aligned with the specific problems of the study. The researchers considered the experts' corrections and suggestions for the improvement of the questionnaire items.

Furthermore, the researchers conducted a dry-run to ensure item reliability. There were 30 selected students who served as the respondents. The Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient test identified the reliability of each item. This test would check if multiple-question Likert's scale surveys are reliable and would tell how closely related a set of test items are as a group. The test was treated and analysed to verify the internal consistency reliability of the items. Generally, a score of more than 0.70 alpha value is "acceptable". The results revealed the following Cronbach's Alpha Coefficients: 0.821 for insufficient sorting of SW; 0.922 for low awareness of proper SWM, 0.842 for poor dumping practices, 0.834 for poor coordination on proper SWM, 0.733 for attitude, and 0.898 for 7R's. These figures indicated that the items in every variable are reliable.

Research procedure. After the design hearing, the researchers incorporated all the corrections and recommendations of the panel members. A request letter to conduct the study was sent to the university president through the vice president for academic affairs of Negros Oriental State University Main Campus I. The signed and approved request was presented to the respective instructors of the students. During the distribution, the researchers explained to the students the purpose and importance of the research. The questionnaires were retrieved right after the students answered the questions.

Accordingly, the results were tallied, analysed, and interpreted using MS Excel software.

Statistical Treatment of the Data. The tools used by the researcher in analysing the data are the following:

Weighted mean. This was used in getting the extent of students' practices and problems on waste management at home.

Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient. This was utilized to identify the relationship between the (a) practices and the problems encountered by the students on waste management; (b) profile (age, educational attainment of parents, and family monthly income) of the students and their practices on waste management at home; and (c) profile (age, educational attainment of parents, and family monthly income) of the students and their problems encountered on waste management at home. This test was selected since one of the data was measured in ordinal scale.

Chi-square. This was used to identify the relationship between the (a) profile (sex) of the students and their practices on waste management at home; and (c) profile (sex) of the students and their problems encountered on waste management at home. This test was selected since sex is a nominal scale.

To identify the degree of relationship between two variables, the researcher applied the following descriptions (Statistical Correlation, 2009):

	Value of r	Strength of Relationship
Between	± 0.50 to ± 1.00	± strong relationship
Between	± 0.30 to ± 0.49	± moderate relationship
Between	± 0.10 to ± 0.29	± weak relationship
Between	± 0.01 to ± 0.09	± very weak relationship

The following interpretations were utilized by the researcher to describe the extent of problems encountered by the students on solid waste management at home:

Verbal Description	Level of Problems	Explanation
Very Serious Problem	Very High	The problems are encountered by the students 81% -100% of the time
Serious Problem	High	The problems are encountered by the students 61% - 80% of the time
Moderate Problem	Moderate	The problems are encountered by the students 41% -60% of the time
Minor Problem	Low	The problems are encountered by the students 21% - 40% of the time
Not at all a problem	Very Low	The problems are encountered by the students 1% - 20% of the time

The following interpretations were applied by the researcher to describe the extent of practices of the students on solid waste management at home:

Verbal Description	Level of Practices	Explanation
Always	Very High	The practices are done by the students 81% - 100% of the time
Often	High	The practices are done by the students 61% - 80% of the time
Sometimes	Moderate	The practices are done by the students 41% - 60% of the time
Rarely	Low	The practices are done by the students 21% - 40% of the time
Never	Very Low	The practices are done by the students 1% - 20% of the time

Scope of the study. This research is focused on determining the extent of problems encountered by the students on solid waste management at home, their extent of practice on solid waste management at home, the demographic profile of the students, and how these variables correlate with each other. The data gathered were utilized to assess and analyze the positive and negative practices and problems students face in managing their solid waste at home. The respondents are the first-year to fourth-year BS Agriculture and BS Forestry students from Negros Oriental State University - Pamplona Extension.

Limitations of the study. The researcher assumes honesty by the respondents in answering the questionnaire. Other factors, which are out of her control, such as the student's attitude, physical, and emotional conditions while answering the questionnaire were also set as limitations of the study. The different settings of their homes where the study was focused might also affect their responses; hence, they were considered as a limitation too.

RESULTS

Table 1.1
Extent of Problems Encountered by the Students on Solid Waste Management at Home in Terms of Insufficient Sorting of SW (n = 169)

Problems	$w\bar{x}$	VD	EoP
1. Biodegradable wastes are mixed with non-biodegradable wastes during collection.	3.61	SP	H
2. Various types of waste are dumped in vacant lots.	3.51	SP	H
3. Recyclable and non-recyclable household waste materials end up being incinerated or dumped in landfills.	3.43	SP	H
4. Unavailability of recycling facilities.	3.38	MP	M
5. Limited space to store household recyclable materials.	3.11	MP	M
6. Only one trash bin is available at home.	2.93	MP	M
Composite	3.33	MP	M

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description (VD)	Extent of Problem (EoP)
	4.21 – 5.00	Very Serious Problem (VSP)	Very High (VH)
	3.41 – 4.20	Serious Problem (SP)	High (H)
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderate Problem (MP)	Moderate (M)
	1.81 – 2.60	Minor Problem (MP)	Low (L)
	1.00 – 1.80	Not at all a Problem (NaP)	Very Low (VL)

Table 1.2

Extent of Problems Encountered by the Students on Solid Waste Management at Home in Terms of Low Awareness of Proper SWM (n = 169)

Indicators	$w\bar{x}$	VD	EoP
1. Lack of awareness in the proper disposal of hazardous waste.	3.49	SP	H
2. Lack of awareness in segregating biodegradable, non-biodegradable, and hazardous waste.	3.45	SP	H
3. Lack of knowledge on the effects of municipal solid waste (MSW) on public health and environment.	3.43	SP	H
4. Improper collection of waste by waste collectors due to the lack of knowledge in solid waste management.	3.41	SP	H
5. Uncollected wastes due to the lack of knowledge in waste segregation.	3.40	MP	M
Composite	3.44	SP	H

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description (VD)	Extent of Problem (EoP)
	4.21 – 5.00	Very Serious Problem (VSP)	Very High (VH)
	3.41 – 4.20	Serious Problem (SP)	High (H)
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderate Problem (MP)	Moderate (M)
	1.81 – 2.60	Minor Problem (MP)	Low (L)
	1.00 – 1.80	Not at all a Problem (NaP)	Very Low (VL)

Table 1.3

Extent of Problems Encountered by the Students on Solid Waste Management at Home in Terms of Poor Dumping Practices (n = 169)

Problems	$w\bar{x}$	VD	EoP
1. Drainage obstruction in households due to improper waste disposal.	3.51	SP	H
2. Scattering of wastes outside the house due to stray cats or dogs rummaging over garbage bins.	3.49	SP	H
3. Possibility of soil and water contamination due to a large amount of solid waste dumped in one place.	3.46	SP	H
4. Backyard became a breeding ground for insects due to open dumping.	3.41	SP	H
5. Recyclable materials ending up in dumpsites.	3.35	MP	M
6. Offensive odor from dumpsites in our locality.	3.34	MP	M
Composite	3.43	SP	H

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description (VD)	Extent of Problem (EoP)
	4.21 – 5.00	Very Serious Problem (VSP)	Very High (VH)
	3.41 – 4.20	Serious Problem (SP)	High (H)
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderate Problem (MP)	Moderate (M)
	1.81 – 2.60	Minor Problem (MP)	Low (L)
	1.00 – 1.80	Not at all a Problem (NaP)	Very Low (VL)

Table 1.4

Extent of Problems Encountered by the Students on Solid Waste Management at Home in Terms of Poor Coordination on Proper SWM (n = 169)

Indicators	w \bar{x}	VD	EoP
1. Laws and regulations that deal with the operations of landfills are often taken for granted.	3.56	SP	H
2. Laws about waste management are unclear to the citizens.	3.55	SP	H
3. Local authorities are very lenient when it comes to the regulation of toxic substances.	3.44	SP	H
4. Public involvement is not encouraged in creating solid waste management policies.	3.41	SP	H
5. "No segregation, no collection policy" is not strictly followed by household members.	3.39	MP	M
6. Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000 (RA 9003) is not implemented within the municipalities.	3.29	MP	M
Composite	3.44	SP	H
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description (VD)	Extent of Problem (EoP)
	4.21 – 5.00	Very Serious Problem (VSP)	Very High (VH)
	3.41 – 4.20	Serious Problem (SP)	High (H)
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderate Problem (MP)	Moderate (M)
	1.81 – 2.60	Minor Problem (MP)	Low (L)
	1.00 – 1.80	Not at all a Problem (NaP)	Very Low (VL)

Table 1.5

Extent of Problems Encountered by the Students on Solid Waste Management at Home in Terms of Attitude (n = 169)

Indicators	w \bar{x}	VD	EoP
1. I believe burning of waste can be bad for my health and the health of household members.	3.66	SP	H
2. I keep our surroundings clean to prevent infectious diseases and potential breeding grounds of insects caused by improper disposal of solid waste.	2.98	MP	M
3. I do not have time to participate in solid waste management drive.	2.96	MP	M
4. I find solid waste management as an extra hassle to be done at home.	2.91	MP	M
5. I am willing to practice solid waste management.	2.85	MP	M
Composite	3.07	MP	M
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description (VD)	Extent of Problem (EoP)
	4.21 – 5.00	Very Serious Problem (VSP)	Very High (VH)
	3.41 – 4.20	Serious Problem (SP)	High (H)
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderate Problem (MP)	Moderate (M)
	1.81 – 2.60	Minor Problem (MP)	Low (L)
	1.00 – 1.80	Not at all a Problem (NaP)	Very Low (VL)

Table 2.1
Extent of Practices of the Students on Solid Waste Management in Terms of the 7R's – Rethink (n = 169)

Indicators	$w\bar{x}$	VD	EoP
1. I dispose empty bottles of herbicides, insecticides, and pesticides in the hazardous waste container.	3.79	O	H
2. I separate food waste and vegetable scraps from non-biodegradable wastes after food preparation.	3.72	O	H
3. I only buy plastic containers that are recyclable.	3.60	O	H
4. I practice composting at home to cut down the amount of trash in a landfill.	3.46	O	H
5. I immediately throw away plastic containers from fast foods even when they are recyclable.	2.95	S	M
Composite	3.50	O	H

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description (VD)	Extent of Practices (EoP)
	4.21 – 5.00	Always (A)	Very High (VH)
	3.41 – 4.20	Often (O)	High (H)
	2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes (S)	Moderate (M)
	1.81 – 2.60	Rarely (R)	Low (L)
	1.00 – 1.80	Never (N)	Very Low (VL)

Table 2.2
Extent of Practices of the Students on Solid Waste Management in Terms of the 7R's – Refuse (n = 169)

Indicators	$w\bar{x}$	VD	EoP
1. I prefer to use eco bags when doing groceries in supermarkets.	3.53	O	H
2. I buy products that do the least harm to the environment.	3.44	O	H
3. I bring my own plastic shopping bags when buying in the public market.	3.18	S	M
4. I do not request plastic spoons and forks when ordering food online.	2.99	S	M
5. I request a "no plastic ware" in take-outs from fast food chains whenever I decided to eat at home.	2.91	S	M
Composite	3.21	S	M

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description (VD)	Extent of Practices (EoP)
	4.21 – 5.00	Always (A)	Very High (VH)
	3.41 – 4.20	Often (O)	High (H)
	2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes (S)	Moderate (M)
	1.81 – 2.60	Rarely (R)	Low (L)
	1.00 – 1.80	Never (N)	Very Low (VL)

Table 2.3

Extent of Practices of the Students on Solid Waste Management in Terms of the 7R's – Reduce (n = 169)

Indicators	$w\bar{x}$	VD	EoP
1. I apply the practices in proper waste disposal and the alternatives to reduce them.	3.93	O	H
2. I have separate garbage bins for biodegradable, non-biodegradable and hazardous waste.	3.59	O	H
3. I bury biodegradable wastes underground.	3.36	S	M
4. I prefer to order products online that uses a lot of bubble wraps to secure my package.	3.15	S	M
5. I prefer to order products online that uses brown box packaging instead of bubble wraps.	2.91	S	M
Composite	3.39	S	M
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description (VD)	Extent of Practices (EoP)
	4.21 – 5.00	Always (A)	Very High (VH)
	3.41 – 4.20	Often (O)	High (H)
	2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes (S)	Moderate (M)
	1.81 – 2.60	Rarely (R)	Low (L)
	1.00 – 1.80	Never (N)	Very Low (VL)

Table 2.4

Extent of Practices of the Students on Solid Waste Management in Terms of the 7R's – Reuse (n = 169)

Indicators	$w\bar{x}$	VD	EoP
1. I reuse plastic food containers, ice cream containers, glass jars, and plastic jars to store leftover foods, frozen foods, and food ingredients.	3.94	O	H
2. I collect and reuse plastic shopping or grocery bags.	3.92	O	H
3. I reuse empty 10-L water containers as gardening pots or water buckets.	3.90	O	H
4. I use products that prioritize reuse, recycle, or use environmentally friendly materials.	3.82	O	H
5. I immediately throw away empty rubbing alcohol bottles instead of refilling them.	2.98	S	M
Composite	3.71	O	H
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description (VD)	Extent of Practices (EoP)
	4.21 – 5.00	Always (A)	Very High (VH)
	3.41 – 4.20	Often (O)	High (H)
	2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes (S)	Moderate (M)
	1.81 – 2.60	Rarely (R)	Low (L)
	1.00 – 1.80	Never (N)	Very Low (VL)

Table 2.5

Extent of Practices of the Students on Solid Waste Management in Terms of the 7R's – Repair (n = 169)

Indicators	$w\bar{x}$	VD	EoP
1. I tried to have our television repaired first rather than throwing it out and getting a replacement.	4.24	A	VH
2. I mend my ripped jeans or holes in clothes instead of disposing of it right away.	4.04	O	H
3. I tried to have my smartphone fixed first before deciding to buy a new one to reduce e-waste.	3.97	O	H
4. I prefer our old electric stand fan to have it repaired instead of buying a new one to reduce e-waste.	3.49	O	H
5. I have my computer or laptop repaired as opposed to purchasing a new one.	3.46	O	H
Composite	3.84	O	H
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description (VD)	Extent of Practices (EoP)
	4.21 – 5.00	Always (A)	Very High (VH)
	3.41 – 4.20	Often (O)	High (H)
	2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes (S)	Moderate (M)
	1.81 – 2.60	Rarely (R)	Low (L)
	1.00 – 1.80	Never (N)	Very Low (VL)

Table 2.6

Extent of Practices of the Students on Solid Waste Management in Terms of the 7R's – Regift (n = 169)

Indicators	$w\bar{x}$	VD	EoP
1. I give my old stuffed toys to the younger family members instead of throwing them away.	3.89	O	H
2. I keep old gift wrappers in good condition to be used on wrapping gifts.	3.83	O	H
3. I donate my old clothes to less fortunate families.	3.80	O	H
4. I give “unused things” at home, which are brand new or in good condition to friends.	3.66	O	H
5. I regift old books, magazines, and comics instead of disposing or burning them.	3.43	O	H
Composite	3.72	O	H
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description (VD)	Extent of Practices (EoP)
	4.21 – 5.00	Always (A)	Very High (VH)
	3.41 – 4.20	Often (O)	High (H)
	2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes (S)	Moderate (M)
	1.81 – 2.60	Rarely (R)	Low (L)
	1.00 – 1.80	Never (N)	Very Low (VL)

Table 2.7

Extent of Practices of the Students on Solid Waste Management in Terms of the 7R's – Recycle (n = 169)

Indicators	w \bar{x}	VD	EoP
1. I throw empty plastic containers in a recycling bin.	3.80	O	H
2. I collect organic wastes for composting to be used as fertilizers in the garden.	3.76	O	H
3. I participate in recycling campaigns and waste segregation programs to promote waste management organized by the local government if it is available.	3.28	S	M
4. I deliver our household recyclables to the recycling facilities/establishments.	3.09	S	M
5. I dispose e-waste such as cooling equipment, computers and telecommunications equipment, electronic devices and solar panels, TVs, monitors, screens, and LED bulbs by giving it to a certified e-waste recycler.	3.09	S	M
Composite	3.41	O	H

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description (VD)	Extent of Practices (EoP)
	4.21 – 5.00	Always (A)	Very High (VH)
	3.41 – 4.20	Often (O)	High (H)
	2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes (S)	Moderate (M)
	1.81 – 2.60	Rarely (R)	Low (L)
	1.00 – 1.80	Never (N)	Very Low (VL)

Table 3

Relationship between the Problems and Practices in Solid Waste Management of Students (n = 169)

Students' Problems at Home and Practices of 7R's	r _s	p-value	Decision	Remark
Rethink	0.286	0.001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Refuse	0.328	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Reduce	0.304	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Reuse	0.291	0.000	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Repair	0.146	0.086	Fail to reject H ₀₁	Not significant
Regift	0.215	0.011	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Recycle	0.240	0.004	Reject H ₀₁	Significant

Level of significance = 0.05

Legend:	Value of r	Strength of Relationship (Statistical Correlation, 2009)
	Between ± 0.50 to ± 1.00	± strong relationship
	Between ± 0.30 to ± 0.49	± moderate relationship
	Between ± 0.10 to ± 0.29	± weak relationship
	Between ± 0.01 to ± 0.09	± very weak relationship

Table 4

Relationship between the Profile of the Students and Their Problems and Practices in Solid Waste Management of Students (n = 169)

Variables	r_s	p-value	Decision	Remark
Problems Encountered and...				
Age	0.083	0.329	Fail to reject H_{02}	Not significant
Fathers' Educational Attain.	0.051	0.549	Fail to reject H_{02}	Not significant
Mothers' Educational Attain.	0.177	0.037	Reject H_{02}	Significant
Family Monthly Income	0.021	0.811	Fail to reject H_{02}	Not significant
	χ^2	p-value		
Sex	3.26	0.138	Fail to reject H_{02}	Not significant
Practices and...				
	r_s	p-value		
Age	0.151	0.076	Fail to reject H_{02}	Not significant
Fathers' Educational Attain.	0.066	0.437	Fail to reject H_{02}	Not significant
Mothers' Educational Attain.	0.222	0.008	Reject H_{02}	Significant
Family Monthly Income	0.031	0.719	Fail to reject H_{02}	Not significant
	χ^2	p-value		
Sex	0.480	0.788	Fail to reject H_{02}	Not significant

Level of significance = 0.05

Legend:

Value of r

Between ± 0.50 to ± 1.00

Between ± 0.30 to ± 0.49

Between ± 0.10 to ± 0.29

Between ± 0.01 to ± 0.09

Strength of Relationship (Statistical Correlation, 2009)

\pm strong relationship

\pm moderate relationship

\pm weak relationship

\pm very weak relationship

DISCUSSION

Table 1.1 displays the data on the extent of problems encountered by the students on solid waste management at home in terms of insufficient sorting of SW. It was revealed that the extent of problems encountered in this area is "moderate" with composite $w\bar{x} = 3.33$.

Specifically, the data pointed out that the most common problem encountered by the students is that biodegradable wastes are mixed with non-biodegradable wastes during collection ($w\bar{x} = 3.61$). The result indicated that students have observed improper sorting of waste during garbage collection. The current finding is similar to the result of the study conducted by Ibañez and Torrentira (2022), where each household collected

their wastes in a single container, wherein biodegradables, non-biodegradables, and all other wastes were mixed because people did not bother to segregate them.

Moreover, the students also encountered problems such as various wastes dumped in vacant lots ($w\bar{x} = 3.51$) and recyclable and non-recyclable household waste materials that are incinerated or dumped in landfills ($w\bar{x} = 3.43$). The results indicated that dumping various wastes in vacant lots, landfills, and incinerating recyclable and non-recyclable household waste materials are common problems directly observed at home, which can negatively affect the environment and human health.

The current findings are likewise evident in the conclusions of Domingo and Manoos (2017), which found that in most households in barangays where garbage is not collected, the residents dispose of their wastes improperly by burning, burying, or tossing these into adjacent vacant lots. Furthermore, it is also manifested in the study of Kaza et al. (2018) where they observed that only 7% of the bulk of waste generated is dumped in sanitary landfills.

The table also exhibits that students encountered problems with insufficient sorting of SW due to the following reasons such as the unavailability of recycling facilities ($w\bar{x} = 3.38$), limited space to store household recyclable materials ($w\bar{x} = 3.11$), and only one trash bin available at home ($w\bar{x} = 2.93$). The findings revealed that improper waste sorting is a prevalent problem that students can immediately notice at home. These are likely due to the lack of recycling facilities, limited space to keep recyclables, and only one trash can be available at home.

Similar findings are observed in the study of Nguyen and Tan (2020) which revealed that residents in Bayog, Los Baños, and Laguna are also facing problems on unsegregated solid wastes due to the absence of Materials Recovery Facilities (MRFs). Furthermore, the results are similar to the findings of Coracero et al. (2021) who emphasized that the root causes of solid waste management issues, such as a lack of space for waste disposal, are believed to increase solid waste problems. It is evident in the data that due to deficiency of community involvement, insufficient dumpsite facilities, and dumping of mixed wastes anywhere solid waste management still remain as a pressing concern in the study site.

Presented in Table 1.2 is the data on the extent of problems encountered by the students on solid waste management at home in terms of low awareness of proper SWM. The data revealed that the extent of problems encountered in this area is “high,” as indicated in the composite weighted mean of 3.44.

It can be observed that students agreed that the extent of problem they encountered in indicators 1 to 4 is “high” as shown in its weighted means ranging from 3.41 to 3.49. These include: (a) lack of awareness in proper disposal of hazardous wastes; (b) lack of awareness in segregating biodegradable, non-biodegradable, and hazardous waste; (c) insufficient knowledge on the effects of municipal solid wastes; and (d) improper collection of wastes due to lack of knowledge in SWM respectively. The results reflected that Philippine LGUs lacked SWM capability, awareness, and

enforcement which may cause socioeconomic and environmental problems and health vulnerabilities without proper understanding and awareness of SWM.

Chadar and Keerti (2017) confirmed in their study that environmental problems on pollution, increasing levels of carbon dioxide and methane and rising concerns on health associated problems are caused by solid waste contaminants which are disposed anywhere.

Khalid et al. (2022) presented a similar observation that improper waste disposal is one of the most pressing environmental issues that lead to other problems such as air pollution, water pollution, and soil contamination which can change the ecosystem and threaten human health.

Table 1.3 reveals the data on the extent of problems encountered by the students on solid waste management at home in terms of poor dumping practices. It exposed that generally the extent of problems encountered in this area is “high,” with a composite weighted mean value of 3.43.

It pointed out that students encountered “high” extent of problems with drainage obstruction in households due to improper waste disposal ($w\bar{x} = 3.51$). The result implied that flooding, erosion, and other environmental problems will likely happen when drainages are obstructed due to solid wastes. The current finding is likewise parallel to the study of Chand (2019) where he emphasized that substances like polythene bags and other wastes clog drain pipes, paralyzing the drainage system.

In addition, the data also stipulated that students encountered the following problems in “high” extent such as: (a) scattering of wastes outside the house due to stray cats or dogs rummaging over garbage bins ($w\bar{x} = 3.49$); (b) soil and water contamination due to a large amount of solid waste dumped in one place ($w\bar{x} = 3.46$); and (c) backyard became a breeding ground for insects due to open dumping ($w\bar{x} = 3.41$). Furthermore, it can also be seen from the data that students had “moderate” problems on recyclable materials ending up in dumpsites ($w\bar{x} = 3.35$), and offensive odor from dumpsites in our locality ($w\bar{x} = 3.34$). The results implied that scattered waste, contaminated soil due to SW, backyards becoming insect breeding grounds due to open dumping, recyclable materials ending up in landfills, and offensive odors from landfills can cause environmental pollution, waste of resources, and respiratory problems.

The results coincide to the study of Domingo and Manoos (2017), in which they reported that dumping in vacant lots results in an insect breeding ground, an eyesore to the general public, and produce unpleasant smells. They added that dumping solid wastes in rivers, streams, and oceans in the coastal barangays causes terrible odor and water pollution which hindered fishing and other water activities.

According to Kaza et al. (2018), improperly managed waste pollutes the world's oceans, clogs sewers, causes flooding and transmits diseases through vector breeding. Additionally, 1.6 billion tons of carbon dioxide (CO₂) equivalent greenhouse gas

emissions (GHG) were generated from solid waste treatment and disposal, primarily from open dumping and landfills.

Table 1.4 provides the data on the extent of problems encountered by the students on solid waste management at home in terms of poor coordination on proper SWM. The table depicts that the extent of problems encountered in this area is "high," as indicated in the composite weighted mean value of 3.44. The data exposed that the students found out that: a) laws and regulations that deal with the operations of landfills are often taken for granted ($w\bar{x} = 3.56$); b) laws about waste management are unclear to the citizens ($w\bar{x} = 3.55$); c) local authorities are very lenient when it comes to the regulation of toxic substances ($w\bar{x} = 3.44$); and d) public involvement is not encouraged in creating solid waste management policies ($w\bar{x} = 3.41$) are serious problems.

Since the Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000 (RA 9003) mandates that LGUs must promote and facilitate public participation in developing and implementing integrated solid waste management plans, the results indicated that local government bodies must implement this RA.

The findings of Park and Tucker (2017) and Bungau et al. (2018) are in agreement to the results of the current study when they emphasized that poor information on reducing waste requires specific and comprehensive legislation. They agreed that there must be clear roles and duties and education/awareness campaigns for the citizens to become knowledgeable in the implementation of laws, policies, and procedures relevant to proper SWM.

Furthermore, the students found out that the No segregation, no collection policy is not strictly followed by household members ($w\bar{x} = 3.39$) and the Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000 (RA 9003) is not implemented within the municipalities ($w\bar{x} = 3.29$) and these pose "moderate" problems in their locality. The results indicated that appropriate waste segregation is essential because it reduces the quantity of waste sent to landfills and incinerators, preserves natural resources and saves energy. In addition, the results suggested that local government units are predominantly responsible for implementing and enforcing RA 9003 within their respective jurisdictions.

The current results are evident in the study of Nguyen and Tan (2020), which emphasized that rural regions need for more local policies on solid waste management for its proper operation. This is also congruent to the findings of Galarpe (2017) as he pointed out that the local government entities failed to competently implement RA 9003 due to the absence of institutional waste management structures because of insufficient funds. It is notable from the result that solid waste pollutants and the production of large amounts of trash without an effective waste management system could worsen the problem on SWM if strict regulations governing the treatment and disposal of solid wastes are not properly implemented and regulated.

Table 1.5 discloses the data on the extent of problems encountered by the students on solid waste management at home in terms of attitude. The data suggested that the extent of problems encountered in this area is "moderate" as indicated in the

composite weighted mean value of 3.07. The students found out that burning of waste can be bad for the health and the health of household members ($w\bar{x} = 3.66$) a serious problem. The result suggested that burning waste may release hazardous chemicals and pollutants into the air, harming human health and the environment. Hence, it is crucial to dispose waste effectively by following proper segregation and disposal procedures. The result is in line with the statement of Chen et al. (2020), which stressed that the open burning of wastes produces substantial amounts of dangerous air pollutants that could seriously harm human health, particularly in developing countries.

Moreover, the students found most of the indicators in this area as “moderate” problem with weighted means of 2.85 to 2.95. These include: (a) keeping the surroundings clean;(b) lack to of time to participate in solid waste management drive; (c) solid waste management as an extra hassle; and (d) willingness to practice solid waste management. The findings demonstrated that sustaining a clean environment is essential for preserving a healthy environment and preventing pollution. Nevertheless, some students may lack the time or means to participate in solid waste management campaigns. Others may view solid waste management as an additional burden and be unwilling to implement it.

The current findings likewise are in consonance to the findings of Wang et al., (2021) when they claimed that people’s inefficient solid waste management is due to lack of time to engage in solid waste segregation campaign, absence of punishment and incentive mechanisms, lack of comprehensive waste management services which resulted to improper solid waste disposal. This finding is parallel to the result of the correlational study of Formarejo et al. (2022) as they affirmed that participation strongly correlates with full awareness of RA 9003, level of resources, and level of enforcement adhering to RA 9003.

Table 2.1 presents the data on the extent of practices of the students on solid waste management in terms of the 7R's - rethink. The data exposed that the extent of practices in this area is "high," as indicated in the composite weighted mean value of 3.50. It suggested that students rethink their consumption practices to make more sustainable decisions in solid waste management.

Moreover, the current result is a reflection that the students are aware that empty bottles of herbicides, insecticides and pesticides are hazardous so disposing them to the hazardous waste container is their utmost priority as indicated in its weighted mean value of 3.79. The findings suggested that students are aware of the risks associated with these types of waste and are taking steps to dispose of them correctly. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations (2023), empty pesticide bottles constitute the bulk of hazardous wastes which must be emptied into pesticide containers provided by established collection program for safety purposes.

Meanwhile, it is also apparent that the extent of students' practice in separating food waste and vegetable scraps from non-biodegradable wastes after food preparation ($w\bar{x} = 3.72$) is “high”. The result suggested that students have a great practice on waste

segregation after food preparation. This practice is beneficial because it reduces the amount of SW sent to landfills and incinerators. The current result agrees to the findings of Goswami (2023), in which respondents were sometimes inclined to separate these household food wastes into separate bins for dry and wet wastes, respectively. In addition, most of them occasionally tended to separate these wastes into other categories, such as biodegradable, non-biodegradable, and hazardous. However, some of his respondents never exhibited similar practices to separate recyclable, toxic/hazardous, compostable, organic, soiled, and food waste. These findings emphasized the need for improved awareness and knowledge to implement the household MSW segregation process correctly.

Furthermore, the extent of the students' practice in buying recyclable plastic containers and the practice of composting at home is also "high," as observed in its mean value of 3.60. According to the findings, students who purchased recyclable plastic containers can positively impact the environment. Reusable and recyclable plastic containers reduce the plastics ending up in landfills or the ocean. Parkar et al. (2021) findings stipulated that plastic has become a vital component of daily life because of its adaptability, leading to various uses. However, because it is not biodegradable, the issue occurs when it does not break down in the natural environment.

On the other hand, the extent to which the students practice composting at home is also "high," as observed in its mean value of 3.46, respectively. The result implied that students have good practice in composting at home, which can also aid in reducing landfill waste and greenhouse gas emissions. Hence, this can impact a positive effect on the environment. The current finding matches to the findings presented in the study of Domingo and Manooos (2017), which stressed that composting biodegradable waste is a good practice in reducing these types of wastes.

Meanwhile, the result also reflected that the students' extent of practice in throwing away of plastic containers from fast food is "moderate". The result implied that throwing away food containers from fast food, even moderately, can still have negative environmental impacts and may contribute to littering and accumulated waste generation. Gallego-Schmid et al. (2019) reported that at present, there is a rising global takeout food consumption. Due to their limited recyclability, single-use containers used for takeout food are a significant source of waste and damaging environmental impacts. In order to reduce the adverse environmental effects of fast-food containers, it is crucial to pinpoint the most effective alternatives and opportunities for improvement. Therefore, it is essential to rethink the consequences of solid waste mismanagement and minimize the use of plastic whenever possible to help lessen the problem.

Shown in table 2.2 is the data on the extent of practices of the students on solid waste management in terms of the 7R's - refuse. The data suggested that the extent of practices in this area is "moderate" as indicated in the composite weighted mean value of 3.21. The results suggested that students should make careful purchasing decisions and establish standards to simplify refusing waste.

It is evident from the result that the students are responsible in taking care of their environment as manifested in their “high” extent of practice in using eco bags when doing groceries in supermarkets ($w\bar{x} = 3.53$) and in buying products that do the least harm to the environment ($w\bar{x} = 3.44$). The results implied that students are highly aware of the eco-bag's effectiveness and that purchasing environmentally friendly products is a great practice to reduce their carbon footprint.

Moreover, the extent of the students' practice in bringing their own plastic shopping bags when buying in the public market ($w\bar{x} = 3.18$); not requesting plastic spoons and forks when ordering food online ($w\bar{x} = 2.99$), and requesting a "no plastic ware" in take-outs from fast food chains whenever they decided to eat at home ($w\bar{x} = 2.91$) are “moderate”. The results implied that these practices, although practiced moderately, can still help reduce the amount of plastic waste in landfills and dumpsites, which can cause adverse effects on the environment. However, increased awareness of the 7Rs' refuse among students needs to be improved.

These findings are likewise evident in the study of Tupas and Cacho (2020), when they disclosed that inhabitants in almost all cities and towns in Northern Ilo-ilo are using eco-friendly materials and that people are informed to bring their own eco bags when going to market since the use of plastics in their place is banned.

Table 2.3 depicts the data on the extent of practices of the students on solid waste management in terms of the 7R's - reduce. It revealed that the extent of practice in this area is “moderate” with composite weighted mean of 3.39. The findings showed that the limited awareness of the 7Rs among students is to blame for the moderate level of practice of 'reduce' among students.

This is in congruence to the findings of Domingo and Manoos (2017), who found that majority of the residents in Boac, Marinduque are separating their biodegradable and non-biodegradable wastes but there are still others who are not practicing such. The study of Mihai and Ingrao (2018) pointed out that appropriate waste management is the key to sustaining a bio-economy in the future and in protecting the environment. According to Coracero et al. (2021), RA 9003 on Ecological Solid Waste Management Act emphasized that only segregated wastes can be collected by the garbage collectors and that people should dispose their garbage to the proper containers which are appropriately labeled as compostable, recyclable, not recyclable, or particular waste.

Additionally, the extent of students' practice in burying biodegradable wastes underground ($w\bar{x} = 3.36$) is moderate. The result implied that students who bury biodegradable wastes underground in a moderate manner mean that they are not burying too much waste, leading to soil pollution and other environmental problems. Concerning this, Ali et al. (2021) highlighted the practice of disposing of biodegradable garbage by burying it in landfills as a solution for sustainable waste management. Their study also highlighted how important it is for landfills to be designed and operated to encourage biodegradation of waste that can be biodegraded.

Furthermore, the extent of students' practice is "moderate" in terms of their preference when they order products online that use a lot of bubble wraps to secure the package ($w\bar{x} = 3.15$). The result suggested that students know the adverse environmental effects of bubble wraps. Bubble wraps are not biodegradable because they are composed of plastic. Bubble wraps can take hundreds of years to decompose, which can be detrimental to fauna and the environment. On the other hand, the extent of students' practice is "moderate" in terms of preferring to order products online that use brown box packaging instead of bubble wraps received the lowest weighted mean of 2.91. The findings showed that there is a need for increased awareness among students on using brown boxes instead of bubble wrap since they can decompose naturally and do not cause harm to the environment.

The article on Philippine News Agency (2022) talks about how the pandemic-driven surge in online merchandise sales generate a considerable volume of new plastic waste daily, mainly from the widespread use of "bubble wraps" to package goods ordered by consumers. Apparently, based on the reflected data, though this indicator is just moderately practiced by the students, but then this adds to the pressing concerns on plastics, especially that these wastes are non-biodegradable, and it will take 10 to 1,000 years to decompose them.

Table 2.4 presents the data on the extent of practices of the students on solid waste management in terms of the 7R's - reuse. The data exposed that the extent of practices in this area is "high," as indicated in the composite weighted mean value of 3.71. The findings suggested that students were reusing items more frequently in an effort to reduce pollution and conserve resources.

Specifically, the extent of students' practice in reusing plastic food containers, ice cream containers, glass jars, and plastic jars to store leftover foods, frozen foods, and food ingredients ($w\bar{x} = 3.94$) is high. The result implied that many students are reusing glass jars and other plastic containers for food storage as a means of recycling. This practice not only helps reduce waste but it also helps save money. The study of Masur (2020) supports the current finding that reusing plastic food containers is only beneficial for food storage. On the other hand, Grant and Kaminski (2022) affirm that repeatedly reusing glass containers is secure and practical for recycling.

It also stipulated that the extent of students' practice in collecting and reusing plastic shopping or grocery bags ($w\bar{x} = 3.92$) is high. The result suggested that many students collect and reuse plastic shopping bags or grocery bags in an effort to lessen plastic waste in the environment and find means to recycle them. Accordingly, Combiths (2021) highlighted the numerous methods for reusing plastic grocery bags such that they can be used in lining trash cans, using them as emergency trash bags for the car, using them as wet bags, packing shoes in suitcases, picking up dog poop, stuffing them into shoes and purses to maintain their shape, protecting fragile items during moving, and storing paint brushes or rollers for later use.

In addition, it was also reflected that the extent of students' practice in reusing empty 10-L water containers as gardening pots or water buckets ($w\bar{x} = 3.90$) is high. The

result emphasized that many students knew empty water containers could be reused as gardening or water buckets instead of discarding them. Hence, reusing these types of containers can help decrease the amount of solid waste. The current finding corresponds to the study of Vanheems (2021) when he stressed that farmers are reusing plastic water containers in the garden as environmentally friendly alternative to watering cans. In addition, these empty water containers are a practical method to create a bird feeder, vertical garden, plant pot, greenhouse, birdhouse, self-watering planter, garden scoop, garden tool holder, and garden sieve.

Moreover, the extent of students' practice in using products that prioritize reuse, recycle, or use environmentally friendly materials ($w\bar{x} = 3.82$) is high. The results implied that many students practice reusing environmentally friendly materials to reduce the adverse effect on human well-being and the environment. According to Ulfat et al. (2023), as an economic strategy based on the reuse and regeneration of materials or products, the circular economy model serves as a means of continuing production sustainably or in an environmentally friendly way reverting excessive rates of waste generation and resource consumption.

Furthermore, the extent of students' practice immediately throwing away empty rubbing alcohol bottles instead of refilling them ($w\bar{x} = 2.98$) is moderate. The result showed that this moderate practice among students of throwing away empty rubbing alcohol instead of refilling them can still impact the environment since rubbing alcohol bottles are made of plastic. Just like any other materials made of plastic, rubbing alcohol bottles will also take hundreds of years to decompose. According to Rosenboom, Langer, and Traverso (2022), bioplastics are good alternatives to conventional plastics in terms of their ability to be recycled or composted at the end of their life cycle.

Table 2.5 presents the data on the extent of practices of the students on solid waste management in terms of the 7R's - repair. The data revealed that the extent of practices in this area is "high," as indicated in the composite weighted mean value of 3.84. The result implied that students know that repairing items before discarding them benefits the environment by reducing waste, conserving resources, and saving money, demonstrating a high level of repair practice.

According to the results above, it appeared that the extent of students' practice in trying to have their television repaired first rather than throwing it out and replaced ($w\bar{x} = 4.24$) is "very high". In addition, the extent of students' practice in mending their ripped jeans or holes in clothes instead of disposing of it right away ($w\bar{x} = 4.04$), trying to have their smartphone fixed first before deciding to buy a new one to reduce e-waste ($w\bar{x} = 3.97$), preferring their old electric stand fan to have it repaired instead of buying a new one to reduce e-waste ($w\bar{x} = 3.49$), and having their computer or laptop repaired as opposed to purchasing a new one ($w\bar{x} = 3.46$) are "high". The data indicated that the students are consistent in saving their stuffs for economic and ecological stability. Moreover, it suggested that people should learn how to repair commonplace items rather than purchasing replacements. It also encouraged people to attempt repairs before

discarding items because fixing these belongings can reduce solid wastes and save money.

In addition, Anderson (2021) mentioned that repair is less expensive than purchasing new products with the same functionality. Furthermore, Bateman et al. (2022) recognized that it is essential to repair electronic devices. Abdullah (2021) also added that the “repair” principle allows manufacturers to keep and use products for a longer period of time. The “repair” principle also applies to consumers who own a product and keep it in good condition. These measures save money and benefit the environment in the long run.

Table 2.6 displays the data on the extent of practices of the students on solid waste management in terms of the 7R's - regift. It revealed that the extent of practices in this area is “high” with a composite weighted mean value of 3.72. The results indicated that a high practice of regifting can positively affect the environment by preventing the disposal of unused items. Thus, unused items at home will reduce the amount of trash in landfills.

It can be seen from the data that the students put high regard in giving their old stuff toys to younger family members as illustrated by the weighted mean of 3.89 which means that this indicator was practiced by the students in “high” extent. The result implied that giving old stuffed toys to younger family members instead of throwing them away is a very common practice in many families. Giving old stuffed toys to younger family members can teach them the value of reuse and recycling by demonstrating that old toys can be reused rather than discarded. This kind of practice will help instill essential values they can maintain throughout their lives.

The extent of students’ practice in keeping old gift wrappers in good condition to be used on wrapping gifts ($w\bar{x} = 3.83$) is high. The results indicated that students are highly aware that keeping old gift wrappers in good condition so they can be reused for gift wrapping is an excellent way to reduce waste and assist the environment. The extent of students’ practice in donating old clothes to less fortunate families ($w\bar{x} = 3.80$) and giving “unused things” at home, which are brand new or in good condition to friends ($w\bar{x} = 3.66$) is high. These results indicated that students evaluate the condition of an item prior to discarding it. These practices are an excellent means to reduce waste at the same time, help others.

The same is presented in the findings of Dayrit (2019) who postulated that minimizing trash production, reusing, regifting and recycling waste materials, are attainable waste management strategies that will help reduce the amount of garbage thrown into the environment. The result of the study implied that using the 7R's promotes the management of sustainable resources while reducing the quantity of garbage that needs to be disposed.

The extent of students’ practice in regifting old books, magazines, and comics instead of disposing or burning them ($w\bar{x} = 3.43$) is high. As indicated by the results, students have high awareness that burning old books, magazines, and comics will

increase the quantity of carbon dioxide and other harmful gases in the atmosphere, contributing to air pollution and global warming.

According to Reyna-Bensusan et al. (2018), burning wastes is a bad practice for reducing biodegradable waste because it causes premature deaths in adults due to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. The same is mentioned in the study of Chen, Bodirsky, Krueger, Mishra, and Popp where they emphasized that burning of wastes produces substantial amounts of dangerous air pollutants that could seriously harm the human health particularly in developing countries.

Table 2.7 reveals the data on the extent of practices of the students on solid waste management in terms of the 7R's - recycle. The data stipulated that the extent of practices in this area is "high" as indicated in the composite weighted mean value of 3.41. The result implied that students were highly active in recycling practices. The reason for this could be that students are more environmentally conscious and more likely to take steps to reduce their carbon imprint.

It pointed out that the extent of students' practice in throwing empty plastic containers in a recycling bin ($w\bar{x} = 3.80$) is high. As indicated by this result, students are highly aware that recycling reduces pollution caused by the chemicals used to manufacture these plastic containers. According to Parkar et al. (2021), plastic containers do not break down when exposed to the action of microorganisms. Plastic has become a vital component of daily life because of its adaptability, leading to various uses. However, because it is not biodegradable, the issue occurs when it does not break down in the natural environment. Therefore, it is essential to minimize the use of plastic whenever possible. Plastics can either be recycled or utilized to reach this goal.

The extent of students' practice in collecting organic wastes for composting to be used as fertilizers in the garden ($w\bar{x} = 3.76$) is high. As a result, many students believed that collecting organic waste for composting and using it as garden fertilizer is beneficial, as it reduces waste and provides a natural source of plant nutrients. The current finding is likewise evident in the study of Domingo and Manoo (2017), where the segregation of biodegradable waste, dumping it in a compost pit, and turning it into plant fertilizer is a good practice for reducing biodegradable waste. Reagan (2023) also emphasized that organic wastes can be composted and used as fertilizers in the garden. The study of Coracero et al. (2021) also revealed that people are encouraged to create compost from waste to be used as fertilizer.

The data further unveiled that participating in recycling campaigns and waste segregation programs ($w\bar{x} = 3.28$) is "moderate". The result implied that students are not very active in terms of participation due to the lack of recycling campaigns and waste segregation programs. These campaigns and programs can help students develop environmental awareness and critical thinking skills on recycling and segregating waste properly. Bungau et al. (2018) stated that more information campaigns are essential to inform and educate the general population on the appropriate storage and proper and secure waste disposal. Moreover, Parajuly, Fitzpatrick, Muldoon, and Kuehr (2020) also emphasized that the effectiveness of intervention strategies to encourage pro-

environmental behavior relying on information campaigns is limited. Moreover, beliefs about environmental impacts and the effectiveness of one's action come into play between values and norms. In other words, these beliefs and norms, and thus the willingness to perform a particular action, can be shaped by information.

The extent of students' practice in delivering household recyclables to the recycling facilities ($w\bar{x} = 3.09$) were also practiced in "moderate" extent. The result implied that the delivery of household recyclables to the recycling facilities is not well-practiced due to the absence of these facilities within their municipality. The current finding is supported by the study of Nguyen and Tan (2020), who emphasized that the absence of materials recovery facilities, a type of recycling facility, indicates that RA 9003 still needs to be implemented.

Furthermore, the extent of students' practice in disposing e-waste such as cooling equipment, computers, telecommunications equipment, and others is found to be "moderate" as indicated in its weighted mean of 3.09. The result implied that students need to be made aware of the environmental and health risks associated with e-waste, indicating that their practice in disposing of e-waste is limited. In addition, appropriate disposal facilities and policies need to be improved. The finding of the study of Maphosa (2021) which examines students' awareness and attitude toward e-waste management practices at a Zimbabwean university is in opposition to the result of the current study because as what he had discovered electronic wastes in their country is not properly managed and eventually caused environmental and health degradation. He further revealed the participants in his study acknowledged that lack of awareness, policies, unavailability of collection points, and recycling facilities significantly affect their e-waste management practices.

Table 3 presents the data in identifying the relationship between the problems and practices in SWM of the students. Utilizing Spearman's Rank Order Correlation, the data revealed that the p-values of the practices like rethink ($p = 0.001$), refuse ($p = 0.000$), reduce ($p = 0.000$), reuse ($p = 0.000$), regift ($p = 0.011$), and recycle ($p = 0.004$) are all less than the level of significance (0.05). These findings allowed the rejection of the null hypothesis. This means that a significant relationship existed between the problems encountered by the students and their practices in terms of the enumerated areas. This finding suggested that students who can identify more problems in SWM tend to have higher utilization of the practices like rethink, refuse, reduce, reuse, regift, and recycle. This means that utilizing these practices may help reduce waste and minimize problems in solid waste management.

The current finding is likewise evident in the study of Bautista (2019) which determines the significant relationship between the level of awareness and practices among Filipino college students on solid waste management. The study revealed that the students' level of awareness is influenced by their practices involving appropriate segregation, reduction, and recycling but had no effect on their practices regarding solid waste management, specifically on reuse, and disposal. He added that the students have encountered more problems on solid wastes and that these students use practices such

as adherence to reduce, recycle, rethink, and proper segregation of solid wastes more frequently because they are more aware of the importance of sustainable waste management and the effects of their behavior on the environment. The study of Formarejo, Hernandez, and Grande (2022) reported that Inland resorts have a high degree of awareness of RA 9003, a high level of practice, and a high level of resources at their disposal, a high level of enforcing and adhering to RA 9003. They also concluded that public practice is strongly correlated with awareness, resources, and enforcement.

Moreover, the study of Domingo and Manos (2017) exposed that the residents' responses in Boac, Marinduque anticipating any problems with the solid waste management they currently practice is "high." However, some residents expressed that they do not expect any problems with the solid waste management they currently practice. Furthermore, the practices and problems encountered by residents revealed that most of them have an equal amount of biodegradable and non-biodegradable waste they produce daily from their routine demands. The same is likewise evident in the study of Saguban (2020), where residents' level of involvement and awareness of the solid waste management programs in the barangay is only "high." Next, she also noted that the residents practice waste segregation, but their performance is "not very high." She stressed that the local governments blamed waste generators' lack of awareness and discipline for poor segregation.

Meanwhile, the students' problems in SWM and their practices in terms of repair is not significantly related ($p = 0.086 > \alpha = 0.05$). This connoted that their problems in SWM cannot be considered as a determinant on how they utilize SWM in terms of repair. The result implied that repair is not a determinant of how they utilize SWM since it has the highest practice with a composite weighted value of 3.84 compared to the other 6Rs. This means that students knew that repairing items before discarding them benefits the environment by reducing waste and, at the same time, saving money. This finding is also congruent to the study conducted by Anderson (2021), who pointed out that people tend to discard "broken" products without attempting to find a solution to restore their functionality. It is a fact that the new generation of today lacks the patience of repairing damage belongings because they wanted that these will be thrown away and be replaced by new one without considering what it causes to the environment.

Table 4 shows the data in identifying the relationship between the profile of the students and their problems and practices in SWM. Using Spearman's Rank Order Correlation (r_s) for ordinal profile and Chi-Square Test (χ^2) for nominal profile, it was shown that of all the profile variables, only the educational attainment of the mothers of the students that is significantly related to the problems encountered ($p = 0.037 < \alpha = 0.05$) as well as their practices in SWM ($p = 0.0308 < \alpha = 0.05$). This means that the more educated they become, the more problems in solid waste management they can identify at home.

In addition, students with mothers of higher educational attainment tend to highly utilize the practices on SWM in terms of the 7Rs. It can be observed that students whose mothers are more educated can point out more problems in solid waste management

since aside from the general notion that women are very particular with cleanliness and orderliness, they are also more knowledgeable and aware of the negative impacts that improper waste disposal could bring not only to the environment but also to the family's health. According to Dousti et al. (2017), more women directly encounter household waste problems than men because they believe that women play a vital role in maintaining the household.

Moreover, study of Escario et al. (2020) revealed that women are more engaged in practicing the 3Rs as an efficient strategy in reducing the problem on solid wastes. They added that women are more inclined at reducing and recycling wastes. The findings of Janmaimool (2017) exposed that more respondents with bachelor's degree levels encounter problems in waste management. The same finding was discovered in the study of Escario et al. (2020) when they suggested that highly educated people engage more in 3R behaviors. These findings were also validated in the study of Choon, Tan, and Chong (2017), when they found that his respondents' education level positively correlates to reuse and recycling behaviors.

Conclusions

Aldo Leopold once said, *"We abuse land because we regard it as a commodity belonging to us, but when we see land as a community to which we belong, we may begin to use it with love and respect"*.

The current status of planet earth is deteriorating due to the many environmental problems such as global warming, acid rain, ocean acidification, climate change, improper solid waste management that leads to pollution and many others. All these have reached an alarming level, that, if we will not take appropriate actions, this will result into total environmental degradation.

The results of the study shows that an increased awareness among students on Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000 (RA 9003) is needed which features the formal delegation of SWM to local levels, forced closure of illegal dumpsites, investment in facilities, and minimization and effective treatment of solid wastes. In addition, the reimplementation of NORSU Memorandum Number 12, s. 2018 on improved SWM awareness of students which they can practice at home, interactive lessons integrating SWM, labelled trash bins on the campus, extension program to educate parents on SWM are some of the strategies to instill a culture of transforming responsible waste management among students and help them by reducing waste in their households. Overall, the result emphasized the importance of the 7R's to help solve the problems on SWM and in saving the environment from permanent damage in general.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn, the following are hereby recommended to curriculum developers, school administrators, science instructors and LGU of Pamplona:

Curriculum developers

1. Create a framework for teaching students about environmental issues and sustainability by incorporating solid waste management into the module which includes the 7 environmental principles by Barry Commoner: 1) nature knows best; 2) all forms of life are important; 3) everything is connected to everything else; 4) everything changes; 5) everything must go somewhere; 6) ours is a finite earth; and 7) nature is beautiful and we are stewards of God's creation. This can help reduce the extent of problems encountered by the students in terms of insufficient sorting of SW and Attitude.
2. Provide a curriculum that encourages students to utilize the 7R's practices such as rethink, refuse, reduce, reuse, regift, and recycle. These practices have been shown to have a significant relationship with the problems encountered by the students in terms of solid waste management.

School Administrators

1. Implement the action plan on Home and Campus-Based Solid Waste Management Action Plan in NORSU – Pamplona Extension.
2. Investigate the role of technology in waste management and explore how “waste-to-energy” technology can be used to reduce waste.
3. Conduct an extension program to provide support for mothers with lower educational attainment. This can help reduce the problems encountered by their children in terms of solid waste management.

Science Instructors

1. Create interactive and engaging lessons for students. This can help increase their interest in solid waste management and encourage them to practice proper solid waste management practices at home.
2. Strategize activities that can help students understand the importance of reducing waste and conserving natural resources.
3. Design a module which includes the environmental laws in the Philippines that are related to SWM such as Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000 (RA 9003), Clean Air Act (RA 8749), Clean Water Act (RA 9275), and Toxic Substances and Hazardous and Nuclear Wastes Control Act (RA 6969). This can help ensure that all

students are able to learn and practice proper solid waste management practices at home.

LGU of Pamplona

1. Make an intervention such as providing trash bins with labels for biodegradable, non-biodegradable, and hazardous wastes to help NORSU Pamplona address the issues in SW.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In adherence to the highest ethical standards, the researchers initially obtained approval from the University Research Office's Ethical Committee. Throughout the study, the researchers meticulously followed all relevant practices and guidelines. The data collected is treated with the highest level of confidentiality. To protect the respondents' identities, their names were not disclosed at any stage of the study, including data collection, analysis, and the reporting of results. This ensures the preservation of anonymity and confidentiality.

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